

EFFECT OF MEMBERSHIP OF FARMER-BASED ORGANIZATIONS AND MICROFINANCE SERVICES ON RICE PRODUCTION IN KWALI AREA COUNCIL OF FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the effect of membership of farmer-based organizations and microfinance services on rice production in Kwali Area Council of Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was used to select one-hundred and twenty (120) rice farmers. The study adopted descriptive statistics, Quartile regression and Factor analysis were used to achieve specific objectives. With a mean age of 43 years, the majority of rice farmers in the sampled area were men with 80%, while women were 20%. The result shows that 62.5% of the sampled respondents were member of farmer-based organization. Also, a majority of the respondents had access to financial literacy training from the micro-finance institution with 68% while 31.7% of the respondents had no access to financial literacy. The results of quartile regression reveals that age of the farmers was positively related and statistically significant to rice production at ($p < 0.1$) level of significance at 25 percentile and access to micro saving training was positively and statistically related to quantity of rice produced at ($p < 0.01$) level of significance at 25 percentile. Low literacy level of farmer was a major constraint to sampled farmers. In order to boost rice production in Kwali Area Council, experienced farmers are to be encouraged to produce rice, contract farming should be expanded for smallholder rice farmers to facilitate market access, and younger farmers should be trained to prevent knowledge and skill loss are suggested.

Keywords: Farmer-based Organization, Microfinance Services, Rice, Production.

JEL Codes: Q12, Q13, Q21

1. INTRODUCTION

As one of the principal sources of income for a majority of households in rural areas, agriculture continues to be crucial to Nigeria's socioeconomic growth especially in rice production (Mrindoko, 2022). In reality, as the population of Nigeria increases, the demand for rice consumption increases due to change in dietary choices (Okoroji, Mukokoma & Bwanika, 2022). Although demand for rice has increased, grading and standardization have not produced the desired results when compared to foreign products that the majority of Nigerians prefer. This has led to a significant reliance on imports from other nations, which has a negative impact

on local reserves and jeopardizes national food security goals (Chijioke & Ogugbue, 2025). The majority of smallholder rice farmers are also severely hampered by poor infrastructure and finance, ineffective extension services, lack of access to inputs, and technical stagnation. Because of these issues, locally grown rice is currently less productive and competitive when compared to imported rice (Ukwuaba, Ibe, Onyekwe, Adebayo, Bamijoko, Ukwuaba, and Anayo, 2025).

In order to address these limitations, there is need for urgent creation of farmer-based organization as one out of many achievable institutional methods that can eliminate or reduce the bottleneck facing smallholder rice farmers in Nigeria. According to Khayyati (2020), farmer-based organization is a voluntary membership-based organizations owned and run by farmer associate that support farmers' interests and offering a range of services to improve the standard of their livelihood. Farmers actualize this membership by pooling resources together, exchange pieces of information to increase their bargaining power in inputs supply and output markets through effective farmer-based organization platforms for joint actions.

At the same time, microfinance services serve as financial provisions structured for individuals with low-income or organizations that lack access to regular banking, such as insurance, savings accounts, and small loans (Morduch, 2000). It becomes an indispensable tool for helping smallholder rice farmers to surmount their financial limitations (Alfa & Abdulfatah, 2019). Inconsistent streams of income sources and lack of collateral, small-scale rice farmers are sometimes considered as high-risk farmers by traditional financial institutions due to these incapacitates. In the context of smallholder rice production, the joint impact of microfinance services and farmer-based organization participation is very significant to increase yield and profits. Microfinance services offer the financial resources to put that expertise into reality, while farmer-based organization increases farmers' organizational ability and access to knowledge (Kagan, 2025). When these systems combine effectively together, they can provide synergistic effects that greatly increase rice yields, farmer incomes and improve welfare. However, there is still little empirical data on how farmer-based organization membership and microfinance services interact in particular local contexts. The majority of research has looked at these interventions separately, without considering how their combined impact affects agricultural results such as “The effects of farmers’ organization and access to credit on farmers’ preference for attributes of improved rice varieties in Ekiti State, Nigeria” by Kehinde, Tijani and Ogundeji (2022); “Effects of Micro-Credit Scheme on Rice Production among Smallholder Farmers in Kwali Area Council, Abuja” authored by Obagbemi, Bamidele, Bako, Alabuja, Ajayi, and Sennuga (2022); “Microfinance services and membership of farmerbased organization as drivers of household food security among rice farmers in Niger and Nasarawa States” written by Otitoju and Olaiya (2025) and “Effect of education and membership of farmer-based organisations on commercialization of paddy rice: A guide for public agricultural policies in Nigeria” authored by Otitoju, Ogunlade, and Ibrahim (2025), among others.

This study fills the identified gap by assessing the effect of membership in farmer-based organizations and access to microfinance services on rice production in Kwali Area Council. By focusing on this intersection, the research aims specifically to: describe the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents; examine the respondents’ membership of farmer-based organizations; assess the micro-finance services used by the respondents; analyze the influence of membership of farmer-based organizations and micro-finance services in rice production in the study area; identify the constraints facing the respondents in rice production in the study area.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Human Capital Theory (HCT) serves as the theoretical foundation for this study.

This idea demonstrates how education raises workers' cognitive abilities, which in turn increases their production and efficiency. The study is based on the human capital theory, which was established and conceived by three well-known proponents: Gary Stanley Becker (1964), Theodore Schultz (1961), and Jacob Mincer (1958).

Becker's seminal work, "Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis of Education," contained the macroeconomic development theory that served as the foundation for HCT. According to the theory, Becker considered a variety of capitals, such as education, computer training, medical expenses, the value of honesty and punctuality, and other factors, as markers that promote productivity by improving health, increasing incomes, and enhancing personality. According to Becker, investing in people may be compared to investing in other production tools like mines or factories. This is due to the fact that they give people more money, enhance their health, and lengthen their lives (Sanni & Onokoya, 2025).

This is due to the fact that economists view investments in medical care, education, and training as investments in human capital (Becker, 2011). He also emphasized that the expansion of human capital, not the expansion of physical capital or technological innovation, is what accounts for economic progress. Becker (1993) makes a distinction between general-purpose and firm-specific human capital. Expertise acquired through education and training in accounting practices, management information systems, or other firm-specific knowledge is considered firm-specific human capital. Knowledge acquired through education and training in fields that are valuable to a range of businesses, such as general skills in human resource development, is known as general purpose human capital (Anoruo, Obiakonwamuo & Amarachi, 2025)

In expanding on Becker's ideas, Schultz (1961), another economist, argues that a society should invest in its people by spending money on things like health, education, training, and research that increase their potential for productivity. Human capital, in his opinion, is the value that individuals contribute to an organization. According to Schultz (1979), human capital entails increasing investments in people's education and training, and individual skills can be improved through education and training that effectively alter job performance. In his subsequent research, he aimed to map out how the rate of return from education may be computed in nations with varying income levels and attitudes toward forgoing profits in order to grow human capital (Severine and Lila, 2009).

As a result, it is agreed that the idea recognizes highly skilled employees as a valuable resource for businesses. It is a possible foundation that offers a business a competitive edge over rivals. In order to build and develop human capital, Shultz (1981) considered both natural and learned skills as valuable assets. Therefore, in a contemporary economy, one of the main drivers of economic growth is investing in people, or human capital. Investing in abilities and intrinsic values, he contends, increases organizational productivity.

The productivity of workers in low-skilled occupations is increased by basic reading, according to human capital theorists. They add that the marginal productivity of people in high-skilled professions and positions is increased by instruction that requires logical and analytical reasoning as well as technical and specialized knowledge. Furthermore, the greater the educational opportunities available to society, the higher the level of economic growth and national output.

HCT is relevant in the context of membership in farmer-based organizations and microfinance services and because it demonstrates how investing in groups of people through education, training, and access to farm resources raises farmers' productivity and efficiency. The fact that farmers-based organizations have higher knowledge (knowledge of sharing), skills, and

support structures means that they are more likely to adopt innovations that increase yields. So, one of the main pillars of agricultural development is the development of human capital through financial services and collective organizations.

2.2 Empirical Review

Otitoju and Olaiya (2025) examined microfinance services and membership of farmer-based organization as drivers of household food security among rice farmers in Niger and Nasarawa States, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to sample 300 rice-farming households in Niger and Nasarawa States. Using descriptive and inferential statistics, ordered probit regression, and the household food insecurity access scale, the study reveals key findings: larger household sizes, older household heads, higher education levels, and larger farm sizes negatively affect food security. Conversely, membership of farmer-based organizations, access to microcredit and microsavings, extension services, farm income, and farming experience positively influence food security. The household food insecurity access scale (HFIAS) analysis shows that only 49% of rice-farming households in the study area are food secure.

Otitoju et al. (2025) evaluated the effect of education and membership of farmer-based organizations (FBOs) on rice commercialization in Gwagwalada Area Council, Federal Capital Territory. Cross-sectional data collected from 140 rice farmers were used for this study. The data were collected from 140 rice farmers through multistage sampling technique. The data were analysed using commercialization index and Beta model. The result of the commercialisation index indicates that majority of the farmers highly commercialised rice. The result of the Beta model analysis shows that age of the farmers, education level of the rice farmers, farm size, literacy ratio, household size and membership of farmer-based organisations were important variables that were significant with policy implications. On the results of the constraints militating against rice commercialization in the study area, lack of/adequate credit for rice production, high cost of fertilizer, and lack of or inadequate proper storage facilities were identified as very serious constraints in the study area.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Area

The study was carried out in Kwali Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Kwali is a local government in Abuja (FCT). Kwali Area Council has a total land mass of about 1,700 square kilometers. In the southwest corner of the FCT is where the Area Council is located. It is located between longitude 7.01° east and latitude 8.87° north. With a 1,206 Km² area. The estimate population was 188,000 as of the 2022 projection (City Population, n.d.). It is the rural residence of Dr. Ladi Kwali, a wellknown potter whose likeness currently graces the 20 Naira currency. The residents of Kwali Area Council, which includes 10 wards named Ashara, Dafa, Kilankwa, Kundu, Kwali, Gumbo, Pai, Wako, Yangoji, and Yebu, also engage in other occupations like farming, hunting, and commerce. A Councilor is in charge of each ward. The Federal Government College, the National Mathematical Center Sheda Kwali, and the Sheda Science and Technology Complex are just a few of the significant landmarks that can be found in Kwali Area Council, Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) pump station Awawa and many more.

This study employed a multi-stage sampling procedure to select respondents. The choice of Kwali Area Council was informed by the high concentration of rice farmers in this area of the Federal Capital Territory, purposively selected as the first stage. In the second stage, four wards (Kilankwa, Pai, Wako, & Kwali) were purposively selected out of the ten wards in the council, based on their prominence as farming communities. In the third stage of the procedure, two communities from each of the four wards were randomly selected, giving a total of eight communities. At the final level, using random sampling technique, fifteen farmers were

selected from each of the eight communities, resulting in a total sample size of 120 respondents (equivalent to 30 respondents per ward).

For this study, the data were collected from primary sources. The Federal Capital Territory Agricultural Development Programme (FCT-ADP) zoning pattern served as the basis for the sampling design. A well-designed questionnaire was used to collect data in order to capture information on the effect of membership in microfinance services and farmer-based organizations on rice production. The questionnaire focused on key socioeconomic and institutional variables such as household size, sex, age, farm size, off-farm income/employment, social participation, and educational attainment and constraints facing the respondents in rice production in the study area. The data were obtained between 11th August to 31st August, 2023 (3 weeks).

In this study to achieve the specific objectives, different analytical methods were employed. Summaries of the socioeconomic characteristics of respondents; the respondents' membership of farmer-based organizations and microfinance services were achieved using descriptive statistics. Quartile regression was used on the influence of membership of farmer-based organizations and micro-finance services in rice production and factor analysis was used to identify main challenges that impede rice production in the study area.

3.2 Model Specification

Quartile Regression

$$y_i = x_i\beta_\theta + \varepsilon_{\theta i} \quad \text{--1}$$

Where,

Y_i = Rice produced in kilograms

X_i = Set of explanatory variables ($i= 1,2,3 \dots n$)

β_θ = Parameter vector

$\varepsilon_{\theta i}$ = Error term

then

$$\text{Quant}_\theta (y_i/x_i) = x_i\beta_\theta \quad \text{--2}$$

$$\text{Quant}_\theta (\varepsilon_i/x_i) = 0 \quad \text{-- 3}$$

Where,

$\text{Quant}_\theta (y_i/x_i)$ = It denotes the conditional quartile y_i , conditional on the regressor vector x_i

$\text{Quant}_\theta (\varepsilon_i/x_i)$ = It assumes that $\varepsilon_{\theta i}$ satisfies the quartile restriction

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + \beta_8X_8 + \beta_9X_9 + \beta_{10}X_{10} + \varepsilon \quad \text{--4}$$

Where:

Y = Quantity of rice produced (kilogram)

β_0 = is the intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_{10}$ = parameter vector to be estimated

X_1 = Age of member of farmer-based organization (Years)

X_2 = Household size (Number)

X_3 = Farming experience (Years)

X_4 = Contract farming (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X_5 = Membership of farmer-based organization (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X_6 = Years of membership of farmer-based organization (Years)

X_7 = Farmer-based organization training (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X_8 = Training in financial literacy from microfinance institutions (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X_9 = Access to micro saving training from microfinance institution (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X_{10} = Access to micro insurance from micro finance institution (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

The socioeconomic features of the smallholder rice farmers in the study area are shown in Table 1. The majority of rice farmers in the study area were men (80%), while women were (20%). This result revealed men as the dominant gender in the study area. This result agrees with the findings of Obagbemi et al. (2022) that male rice farmers dominate rice production in the Kwali Area Council, Abuja.

The marital status of the respondents showed that about 91.7% were married, 5% were widowed, and 3.3% were single. This implies that the majority of the sampled respondents have a stable family resource which could be available for family labour if needed. This result is in line with the findings of Onyeneke (2017), who found that married rice farmers were dominant in Imo State, Nigeria. The study revealed that 32.5% of respondents had no formal education, 26.7% had completed secondary education, 20.8% had completed tertiary education, 20.0% had completed primary education and a mean of 8.04 years. This finding corroborates with Bello, Baiyegunhi, and Danso-Abbeam (2021), whose observation showed that farmers' adoption of new practices could be affected by their low level of education in Nigeria. With a mean age of 43 years, the age distribution revealed that 40.8% were within the age bracket of 41 and 50, 23.3% were between the ages of 31 and 40, 21.7% were within the age range of 51 and 60, and 14.2% were between the ages of 21 and 30. This result has it that rice production in the Kwali Area Council is dominated by active and productive farmers. This is consistent with the findings of Ibrahim, Yusuf, Mohammed & Audu (2021) that rice production in the Nigerian North is dominated by middle-aged farmers.

With a mean household size of 7.2, the results showed that 69.2% had 6-10, 23.3% had 1-5, and 7.5% had 11-15 household members. This implies that the sample respondents have more household family members. This corroborates the findings of Adeshina, Ologbon, and Idowu (2020), who discovered that large households are common in rural areas in Nigeria.

In addition, 36.7% of sampled rice farmers had farming experience between 1-5years, 30.8% of rice farmers also had farming experience between 6-10 years, 14.20% had between 11-15 years, and a mean of 9.64. The result agrees with Ariyo Sotayo, Olurin, and Olurunda (2020) who reported that the mean years of farming experience of respondents was 10 years in Ogun State, Nigeria.

About 74.2% had no access to credit, while 25.8% had access to credit in the study area. Also, 62.5% of sampled respondents had an extension visit, and 37.5% had no extension visit in the study area. This result agrees with the findings of Tanko, Kang, and Islam (2019) that extension services become inevitable for spreading agronomic practices.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of the respondents in the Study Area

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean
Male	96	80.0	
Female	24	20.0	
Total	120	100.0	
Marital status			
Single	4	3.3	
Married	110	91.7	
Widow	6	5.0	
Total	120	100.0	
Education Level			
No formal education	39	32.5	
Attended primary school	24	20.0	8 years
Attended secondary school	32	26.7	
Attended tertiary school	25	20.8	
Total	120	100.0	
Age			
21 – 30	17	14.2	
31 – 40	28	23.3	
41 – 50	49	40.8	43 years
51 – 60	26	21.7	

Total	120	100.0	
Household Size (Number)			
1- 5	28	23.3	
6 – 10	83	69.2	7 persons
11- 15	9	7.5	
Total	120	100.0	
Farming Years of Experience			
1-5	13	10.8	
6-10	24	20.0	
11-15	17	14.2	
16-20	12	10.0	19 years
21-25	18	15.0	
26-30	36	30.0	
Total	120	100.0	
Rice Farming Years of Experience			
1-5	44	36.7	
6-10	37	30.8	
11-15	17	14.2	
16-20	15	12.5	9 years
21-25	4	3.3	
26-30	3	2.5	
Total	120	100.0	
Access to Credit			
Access to credit	31	25.8	
No access to credit	89	74.2	
Total	120	100.0	
Extension Visit			
Extension Visit	75	62.5	
No extension visit	45	37.5	
Total	120	100.0	

Source: computed from field data, 2023

Respondent's Membership in Farmer-Based Organization

The frequency and percentage of membership of farmer-based organization of smallholder rice farmers are shown in Table 2. The result showed that 62.5% of the sampled respondents were member of farmer-based organization and 37.5% of the respondent's were not member of farmer-based organization. Furthermore, the analysis on farmer-based organization training showed that 53.35% of the respondents had access to farmer-based training and 46.7% had no access to farm-based training. This implies a majority of the sample had access to farmer-based organization in the study area.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of the Respondents' Membership of Farmer-Based Organization

Membership of Farmer-based Organization	Frequency	Percentage
Membership of farmer-based organization	75	62.5
Non- Membership of farmer-based organization	45	37.5
Total	120	100.0
Farmer-based Organization training		
Farmer-based Organization training	64	53.3
No farmer-based Organization training	56	46.7
Total	120	100.0

Source: computed from field data, 2023

Frequency Distribution of the Respondents by the Microfinance Services Used by the in the Study Area

Table 3 shows the frequency distribution of the analysis of microfinance services used by the respondents. The majority of them had access to financial literacy training from the microfinance institution, with 68%, while 31.7% of the respondents had no access to financial literacy. This outcome indicates that the respondents kept records, had the knowledge to manage their finances better to make informed decisions and could make wise investments.

Analysis of micro-saving training showed that the majority of the respondents had access to micro-saving training from a micro-finance institution of 70.28% and 29.2% of the respondents had no access to micro-saving training from microfinance institution. The implication is that the farmers had developed a savings habit that helped them to build financial resilience and improve their productivity.

Analysis on micro-insurance showed that the majority of the respondents had access to micro-insurance from a microfinance institution of 86.7% and 13.3% of them had no access to micro-insurance training from micro-finance institution. This implies that the respondents could manage production risk, such as crop failure, and in return could reduce their exposure to poverty vulnerability and financial shock.

In addition, the majority of the sample had access to a payment service of 83.3% and 16.7% had no access to a payment service. This implies that financial transactions are easily carried out promptly by the respondents, which could secure their produce timely.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of the Respondents by the Microfinance Services Used by the in the Study Area

Financial literacy training	Frequency	Percentage
Financial literacy training	82	68.3
Non-financial literacy training	38	31.7
Total	120	100.0
Micro saving training		
Micro saving training	85	70.8
No micro saving training	35	29.2
Total	120	100.0
Access to Micro-insurance		
Access to micro-insurance	104	86.7
No access to micro-insurance	16	13.3
Total	120	100.0
Access to payment service		
Access to payment service	100	83.3
No access to payment service	20	16.7
Total	120	100.0

Source: computed from field data, 2023

Influence of Membership of Farmer-Based Organizations and Micro-Finance Services in Rice Production in the Study Area

The findings in Table 4 shows that six out of ten explanatory variables, which include age of member of farmer-based organizations, household size, farming experience, contract farming, farmer-based organization training, and access to micro-saving training from microfinance institution were significant. Furthermore, this Table 4 displays the quartile regression estimates for the 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75 quartiles. Table 4 also shows Pseudo R² of 0.1855, 0.1598 and 0.0810 indicating models' goodness-of-fit at the different quartiles. To ensure the robustness of the findings in Table 4, bootstrap standard errors were employed to correct for potential heteroskedasticity, providing confidence in the reliability of the reported significance levels. This approach is supported by Li and Lawson (2021), who pointed out that bootstrapping provides a powerful means of estimating uncertainty by directly resampling from the data, thereby reducing reliance on potentially fragile theoretical assumptions.

Also, Variance inflation factor (VIF) diagnostics were not employed in this study because the analysis utilized quartile regression rather than ordinary least square regression (OLS). VIF is primarily relevant for OLS models, where multicollinearity inflates variances and undermines inference. Quartile regression, however, does not rely on the same variance assumptions and is robust to heteroscedasticity and non-normality of errors (Koenker & Bassett, 1978; Koenker, 2005). As Hao and Naiman (2007) note, multicollinearity does not invalidate quartile regression estimates, and alternative approaches such as bootstrapped confidence intervals and

sensitivity checks across quartiles are more appropriate. Accordingly, this study relied on pseudo R^2 values and robustness across quartiles to assess explanatory power.

The coefficient of the age of member of farmer-based organizations was significant at 10% level of probability (i.e $p < 0.1$) with positive relationship at the 25th percentile, indicating that an increase in age of member of farmer-based organizations is associated with an increase in rice production. At 50th percentile age of member of farmer-based organizations is positively related and statistically significant at 1% level of probability (i.e $p < 0.01$). This implies that a unit increase in age would lead to an increase in rice production as well. At 75th percentile, the age of member of farmer-based organizations is positively significant at 5% significance level of probability (i.e $p < 0.05$). This implies that a unit increase in age would lead to an increase in rice production meaning that older farmers are more efficient in the production of rice than younger farmers, which can be a result of the experience, skills, and knowledge the older farmers have gained over time. This result agrees with the study of Ouedraogo, Al-hassa, Amegashie, Zahonogo and Sarpong (2018) that established positive relationship of age and smallholders' agricultural commercialization in Burkina Faso.

Table 4 further reveals that the farmers' household size is negatively related and statistically significant at 5% significance level of probability (i.e $p < 0.05$) at 25th percentile. This implies that additional household size is associated with reduced rice production. This finding runs counter to conventional microeconomic theory, which often assumes that larger households size provide more labour and thereby enhances farm productivity. The composition of households may matter more than size. Larger households may include more dependents than active labourers, thereby increasing consumption without contributing proportionally to farm output. This result contrasts Adewumi and Omotesho (2017), who observed that the availability of farm labour in rural areas was positively impacted by larger households.

In addition, Table 4 reveals that farming experience is positively and statistically significant at 5% significance level of probability (i.e $p < 0.05$) at 25th percentile. This implies increase in farming experience would lead to increase in rice production. This shows that farmers with more farming experience are more productive in rice production. Farming experience is a very vital variable in production because the more the experience of a farmer in farming the more he knows the right skills, techniques, best farming practice to use to increase rice production. This result supports the findings of Eze and Okoye (2020), who stated that agricultural experience enhances smallholder farmer's production.

Contract farming is positively and statistically significant at 1% level of probability (i.e $p < 0.01$) at 25th percentile. This implies an increase in farming experience leads to increase in rice production. At 50th percentile, contract farming is positively and statistically significant at 10% level of probability (i.e $p < 0.1$). This implies increase in contract farming would lead to increase in rice production. Contract farming serve as an important variable in rice production. So, farmers would try to work hard in farming to meet the stated agreement as a result of the the fact that risk and loss would be shared.

Access to microsaving training as shown in Table 4 is positively and statistically significant at 1% level of probability (i.e $p < 0.01$) at 25th percentile. This implies increase in access to microsaving training would lead to increase in rice production. Micro saving training is essential in rice production because it helps the farmers to utilize and allocate micro-credit efficiently and this can result to increase in rice production. This finding agrees with the finding of Biala and Galadima (2023) that savings programs and other microfinance services increase farmers' ability to invest in better inputs.

Table 4 shows that farmer-based organization training is negatively and statistically significant at 10% level of probability (i.e $p < 0.1$) at the 50th percentile, suggesting that increased training participation corresponds with lower output. This finding contradicts the *a priori* expectation

that training should enhance productivity. Several explanations may account for this result. First, farmers who participate in such training may not consider rice farming their primary occupation, instead diversifying into other crops or non-farm activities. Second, training programmes may emphasize broader agricultural or organizational skills rather than rice-specific practices, leading to limited direct benefits for rice production. This result contrasts with Otitoju and Olaiya (2025), who reported that farmer-based organization training improved rice productivity and food security in Niger and Nasarawa States.

Table 4: The Quartile Regression Result of the Influence of Membership of Farmer-Based Organizations and Micro-Finance Services in Rice Production in the Study Area

Explanatory Variables	0.25		0.50		0.75	
	Coefficient	t-value	Coefficient	t-value	Coefficient	t-value
Age of member of farmer-based organizations (Years)	1905.898* (1055.837)	1.81	5814.139*** (1923.637)	3.02	9636.449** (4729.082)	2.04
Household size(Number of persons in the household)	-7096.829** (3508.929)	-2.02	-2562.013 (6392.942)	-0.40	-5885.249 (15716.45)	-0.37
Farming experience (years)	2026.935** (1009.845)	2.01	437.6329 (1839.844)	0.24	210.4505 (4523.082)	0.05
Contract farming (Dummy)	142993.5*** (43907.19)	3.26	151987.2* (79994.81)	1.90	132343.5 (196659.7)	0.67
Membership of farmer-based organization (Dummy)	-14246.51 (32241.17)	-0.44	-31772.68 (58740.4)	-0.54	11870.55 (144407.8)	0.08
Years of membership of farmer-based organization (years)	-5633.311 (4383.039)	-1.29	8505.847 (7985.489)	1.07	10092.88 (19631.57)	0.51
Farmer-based organization training (Dummy)	12806 (19922.15)	0.64	-71273.92* (36296.3)	-1.96	-57579.2 (89231.05)	-0.65
Training in financial literacy from microfinance institutions (Dummy)	-7064.439 (28823.61)	-0.25	-15194.9 (52513.94)	-0.29	66733.73 (129100.6)	0.52
Access to microsaving training from microfinance institution (Dummy)	76797.65*** (26751.74)	2.87	73515.24 (48739.18)	1.51	-27292.2 (119820.7)	-0.23
Access to micro-insurance from micro finance institution (Dummy)	1772.929 (9144.41)	0.19	-10671.8 (16660.26)	-0.64	-22590.18 (40957.69)	-0.55
Constant	10903.51 (40577.94)	0.27	-68921.86 (73929.23)	-0.93	-127015.3 (181748.1)	-0.70
Diagnostic Statistics:						
Pseudo R²	0.1855		0.1598		0.0810	

*** significance at 1% level; ** significance at 5% level; * significance at 10% level.

Figures in parentheses are bootstrap standard errors.

Source: computed from field data, 2023

Constraints Facing Respondent's in Rice Production in the Study Area

Table 5 shows the constraints facing respondents in rice production in Kwali area council. Low literacy level of farmer was a major constraint with 65.0% of the rice farmers attested that it was a very serious challenge, 40% of them attested to it as a serious constraint, 1.7% of them confirmed it as a less serious problem and 0% of the respondents believed it not to be a critical challenge indicating that no one believes it is a serious problem. Also, 65.0% of them strongly agreed to the low financial level of farmers as a very serious constraint, 34.2% of the respondents attested that it is a serious constraint, none (0%) of them confirmed it as a less serious problem and 0.8% of the respondents believed it not to be a serious problem. Also, 57.5% of them agreed that difficulty in access to micro-finance services was a very serious constraint, 40.8% of them attested to it as a serious constraint, 1.7 % attested that it is a less serious constraint and none (0%) of them attested that it is not a serious constraint. This supports the findings of Otitoju and Olaiya (2025), who observed that rice farmers' capacity to invest in better inputs was hampered by their restricted access to microfinance services. Also, 38.3% of the respondents agreed that high value of collateral is a very serious problem, 59.2% of them attested that it is a serious problem and 2.5% of them attested that it is a less serious problem and none (0%) of them believed it not to be a serious problem. This result aligns with the findings of Adam, Ashiko, Ogbanje, and Okeke (2024), who noted that institutional credit markets frequently exclude smallholder farmers due to collateral demands. More so, 49.2% of the respondents agreed that high loan interest rate is a very serious constraint, 45.8% of them agreed that it is a serious constrain and 4.2% of them agreed that it is a less serious constraint and 0.8% of them believed it not to be a serious problem. Again, 50.8% of the respondents agreed that bureaucratic processes in accessing credit from the scheme is a very serious constraint, 40.8% of them agreed that it is a serious constraint, 7.5% of them agreed that it is a less serious constraint and 0.8% of the respondents believed it not to be a serious problem.

In the same vein, 40% of the respondent agreed that strict regulations and guidelines to access credit from micro-finance services is a very serious problem, 52.5% of them agreed that it is a serious problem, while 7.5% agreed that it is a less serious constraint and none (0%) of the respondents believed it not to be a serious problem. Also, 36.7% attested that Credit rationing by micro-financial institutions is a very serious constraint 55.8% of them attested that it is a serious constraint, 6.7% of them attested that it is a less serious constraint, while 0.8% of them believed it not to be a serious problem. Also, 39.2% of the respondent believed that Difficulty of access to micro-financial markets is a very serious constraint, 43.3% of them believed that it is a serious constraint, 17.5% of them believed that it is a less serious constraint, while none (0%) of them believed that it is not a serious constraint. More so, 49.2% of the respondents agreed that Inadequate agricultural extension and advisory services, 31.7% of them agreed that it is a serious problem, 18.3% of them agreed that it is a less serious problem, while 0.8% of them agreed that it is not a serious problem. Also, 43.3% of the respondents agreed that inadequate rice processing facilities is a very serious constraint, 42.5% of them agreed that it is a serious constraint, 14.2% of them agreed that it is a less serious constraint and none (0%) of them agreed that it is not a serious problem. Also, 36.7% of the rice farmers attested that lack of / inadequate proper storage facilities is a very serious problem, 30.8% of them attested that it is a serious problem, 31.7% of them attested that it is a less serious problem and none (0%) of them agreed that it is not a serious problem. Also, 28.3% of the rice farmers attested that inadequate marketing information is a very serious problem, 34.2% of them attested that it is a serious problem, 37.5% of them attested that it is a less serious problem and none (0%) of them agreed that it is not a serious problem. This supports the claim made by Ibrahim and

Bello (2019) that farmers' bargaining power and profitability are weakened for not having a required access to market information.

Frequency Distribution of Constraints Facing Respondents in Rice Production in the Study Area

S/No	Items	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Mean (standard deviation)
1.	Low literacy level of farmers	78 (65.0)	40 (33.3)	2 (1.7)	0 (0)	3.6333 (0.51748)
2.	Low Financial level of farmers	78 (65.0)	41 (34.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.8)	3.6333 (0.53347)
3.	Difficulty in access to micro-finance services	69(57.5)	49(40.8)	2(1.7)	0(0)	3.55583 (0.53130)
4.	High value of collateral	46(38.3)	71(59.2)	3(2.5)	0(0)	3.3583 (0.53130)
5.	High loan interest rate	59(49.2)	55(45.8)	5(4.2)	1(0.8)	3.4333 (0.61812)
6.	Bureaucratic processes in accessing credit from the scheme	61(50.8)	49(40.8)	9(7.5)	1(0.8)	3.4167 (0.66842)
7.	Strict regulations and guidelines to access credit from micro-finance services	48(40.0)	63(52.5)	9(7.5)	0(0)	3.3250 (0.61031)
8.	Credit rationing by micro-financial institutions	44(36.7)	67(55.8)	8(6.7)	1(0.8)	3.2833 (0.62421)
9.	Difficulty of access to micro-financial markets	47(39.2)	52(43.3)	21(17.5)	0(0)	3.2167 (0.72394)
10.	Inadequate agricultural extension and advisory services	59(49.2)	38(31.7)	22(18.3)	1(0.8)	3.2750 (0.79876)
11.	Inadequate rice processing facilities	52(43.3)	51(42.5)	17(14.2)	0(0)	3.2917 (0.70289)
12.	Lack of / inadequate proper storage facilities	44(36.7)	37(30.8)	38(31.7)	1(0.8)	3.0333 (0.84945)
13.	Inadequate marketing information	34(28.3)	41(34.2)	45(37.5)	0(0)	2.9083 (0.80956)

Source: computed from field data, 2023

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the impact of microfinance services and membership in farmer-based organizations on rice farmers in Kwali Area Council of Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria. The results showed that farmer-based organizations membership and the usage of microfinance services were highly influenced by variables including household size, age, contract farming, farming experience, farmer-based organizations training, as well as access to micro-saving training. Even so, there were some challenges that rice farmers in the study area had to deal with, such as low literacy rates, a lack of financial resources, trouble obtaining microfinance services, high loan interest rates, bureaucratic credit access procedures, poor extension services, and inadequate processing and storage facilities.

In order to increase rice production in Kwali Area Council, contract farming should be increased for smallholder rice farmers for easier market access, encouragement be given to experienced farmers to cultivate rice, and younger ones be trained to prevent knowledge and skill loss. While microfinance firms offer micro-savings training to guarantee efficient use of credit, the government and non-government organizations should design a framework as a training-hub for farmer-based organizations. If implemented, the production of rice will increase sustainably as a result of these joint efforts.

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